

Grant Agreement No: 951754

FCCIS

Future Circular Collider Innovation Study

Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Framework Programme, Research and Innovation Action

MILESTONE REPORT

PROGRESS REVIEWED 2

Document identifier:	FCCIS-P2-WP1-MS7
Due date:	End of Month 21 (August 2022)
Date:	05/08/2022
Work package/unit:	WP1 Management
Organisation:	CERN
Version:	V1.0
Status:	RELEASED
Keywords:	Project management and coordination, review

Abstract:

Agenda and draft minutes of board meetings available in document management system. Work progress reviewed and aligned in the form of FCC Week 2022 in Paris with presentations publicly available on Indico (Green). Open Access proceedings publication with SN (Gold) completed.

Copyright notice:

Copyright © FCCIS Consortium, 2020

For more information on FCCIS, its partners and contributors please see <https://twiki.cern.ch/twiki/bin/view/FCC/FCCIS>.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 951754.

Delivery Slip

	Name	Organisation	Date
Authored by	Panagiotis Charitos, Julie Hadre	CERN	29/07/2022
Edited by	David Goldsworthy	CERN	01/08/2022
Approved by	Michael Benedikt	CERN	01/08/2022

TABLE OF CONTENTS

1. INTRODUCTION.....	4
2. FCCIS GOVERNANCE BODIES MEETINGS	5
2.1. GENERAL ASSEMBLY.....	5
2.2. EXECUTIVE BOARD.....	6
3. FCC REVIEWS	7
3.1. REVIEW OF FCC PLACEMENT STUDIES	7
3.1.1. <i>Scope of the review</i>	8
3.1.2. <i>Review goals and charge</i>	8
3.1.3. <i>Reviewers</i>	8
3.1.4. <i>Agenda</i>	8
3.1.5. <i>Conclusions</i>	9
3.2. PRE-ENGINEERING DESIGN REVIEW AND ROADMAP DISCUSSION FOR FCC-EE IR MAGNETS.....	9
3.2.1. <i>Scope of the review</i>	9
3.2.2. <i>Review goals and charge</i>	10
3.2.3. <i>Reviewers</i>	10
3.2.4. <i>Agenda</i>	10
3.2.5. <i>Conclusions</i>	10
4. FCC ANNUAL MEETINGS.....	11
5. CONTRIBUTIONS FOR OPEN ACCESS PROCEEDINGS PUBLICATION.....	12

1. INTRODUCTION

Following its approval, the FCCIS project held its kick off meeting in November 2020, coupled to the 4th FCC physics week in the “FCC November Week 2020” (FCC NoW 2020). This meeting reviewed the challenges to deliver an implementation plan and a feasibility study for a new Research Infrastructure based on a new tunnel of ~100 km circumference, that could successively host an electron-positron (FCC-ee) and proton-proton collider (FCC-hh). The meeting, hosted virtually, offered numerous opportunities for cross-talks between the different scientific communities that are coming together under the FCCIS project. During FCC NoW the first FCCIS General Assembly meeting and Executive Board meeting took place, defining the key priorities and tasks for each of the project WPs and all participating members.

In addition, during the first reporting period, the FCCIS WP1 successfully organized two reviews with panels of international experts, validating the approach adopted by the FCC study management and offering an independent evaluation and critical guidance for the next steps. The first of these meetings focused on the FCC ee pre-injector complex and the second on the design of FCC-ee SRF cavities, which is one of the most critical accelerator components for the overall machine performance and efficiency. Further reviews of other key areas will take place in the subsequent months.

During the second year of the FCCIS Design Study activities in all work packages progressed as planned. Another FCC Physics Workshop was organised in Liverpool as hybrid event in February 2022. The entire study progress was presented during the FCC Week 2022 taking place in Paris end May – beginning of June 2022.

Since last Progress Reviewed report dated June 2021, the following events have taken place:

- 07-08 June 2021: Review of FCC placement studies (hybrid mode, CERN Switzerland) [Revue des études de placement FCC / Review of FCC placement studies \(7-8 June 2021\) · Indico \(cern.ch\)](#)
- 04-05 April 2022: Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets (Hybrid mode, CERN Switzerland) [Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets \(4-5 April 2022\) · Indico \(cern.ch\)](#)
- 28 June – 02 July 2021: Annual meeting FCC Week 2021 (remote) <https://indico.cern.ch/e/fccw2021>
- 07 – 11 February 2022: FCC Physics Workshop (originally on site in Liverpool) [FCC Physics Workshop \(7-11 February 2022\): Overview · Indico \(cern.ch\)](#)
- 30 May – 03 June 2022: Annual meeting FCC Week 2022 (hybrid mode, Paris, France) <https://indico.cern.ch/e/fccw2022>

Table 1: Relevant project meetings during the period 01 June 2021 – 31 July 2022

Dates	Type of meeting	Venue	Attendance	Indico link
07/06/2021	Review	Hybrid (CERN and remote)	Reviewers and presenters	Review of FCC placement studies
28/06-02/07/2021	Annual meeting	Remote	FCC and FCCIS members	FCC Week 2021
29/11-10/12/2021	Workshop	Hybrid (CERN and remote)	WP2 members	FCCIS WP2 Workshop 2021
04/04/2022	Review	Hybrid (CERN and remote)	Reviewers and presenters	Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets

30/05-03/06/2022	Annual meeting	Hybrid format (Paris, France, and remote)	FCC and FCCIS members	FCC Week 2022
-------------------------	----------------	---	-----------------------	-------------------------------

2. FCCIS GOVERNANCE BODIES MEETINGS

2.1. GENERAL ASSEMBLY

The General Assembly (GA) is the highest-level decision-making body in the FCCIS project. All the GA members are listed here: [FCCISGeneralAssemblyMembers < FCC < TWiki \(cern.ch\)](#)

The GA members have been requested to endorse the second instalment of the prefinancing that was due at the end of the first year of the project after submission of all deliverables and reports.

General Assembly Board Members

The following table lists all appointed General Assembly board members.

The status of currently active board members is **Active**.

Board members can change. In this case, the status of the previously active board member becomes **Inactive**.

The date indicates when a board member becomes active.

The contact details are at least an e-mail address and a phone number.

Organisation	Representative Full Name	E-mail	Phone	Date	Status
CERN	Michael Benedikt	Michel.benedikt [at] cern.ch	+41 22 767 3380	2020-09-24	Active
CEA	Pierre Vedrine	pierre.vedrine [at] cea.fr		2020-10-21	Active
Cerema	Pierre Biollon	Pierre.Boillon [at] cerema.fr	+33 6 22 34 87 95	201022	Active
CETU	Eric Premat	eric.premat [at] developpement-durable.gouv.fr	+33 4 72 14 33 85	2020-10-19	Active
CNRS	Giovanni Lamanna	giovanni.lamanna [at] lapp.in2p3.fr	+33 4 50 091 600	2020-10-02	Active
CSIL	Emanuela Sirtori	sirtori [at] csilmilano.com	+39 284 105 514	2020-10-02	Active
DESY	Wim Leemans	wim.leemans [at] desy.de	+49 40 8998 4427	2020-10-19	Active
IFJ PAN	Marcin Chrzyszcz	marcin.chrzyszcz [at] cern.ch	+41 22 767 4042	2020-10-05	Active
INFN	Manuela Boscolo	manuela.boscolo [at] Inf.infn.it	+39-339 52 95 160	2020-10-06	Active
KIT	Anke-Susanne Müller	anke-susanne.mueller [at] kit.edu	+49 7251 3 58 91 56	2020-10-16	Active
LD	Maude Sauvain	maude.sauvain [at] latitudedurable.ch	+41 764 453 615	2020-10-05	Active
MUL	Robert Galler	robert.galler [at] unileoben.ac.at	+43 664/2101607	2020-10-05	Active

Figure 1 – Screenshot of the Twiki page FCCIS General Assembly members

2.2. EXECUTIVE BOARD

The Executive Board (EB) implements the decisions of the General Assembly and proposes changes in the project and consortium plan to the GA, including changes of the CA and GA annexes.

The EB meets monthly, via the Zoom videoconferencing system. The EB consists of the Project Coordinator (PL and deputy), Work Package Leaders and their deputies.

The EB members are compiled at: [FCCIS Executive Board Members < FCC < TWiki \(cern.ch\)](#)

For each meeting, the agenda, list of participants and the minutes are posted in the Indico category [FCCIS Executive Boards · Indico \(cern.ch\)](#), with access restricted to the EB members.

10 Executive Boards meetings took place between June 2021 and July 2022 as shown in Table 2 :

Table 2: List of Executive Boards meeting during the period 01 June 2021 to 31 July 2022

Dates	Type of meeting	Venue	Attendance	Indico link
24/06/2021	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 07
29/07/2021	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 08
26/08/2021	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 09
23/09/2021	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 10
28/10/2021	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 11
25/11/2021	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 12
13/01/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 13
10/03/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 14
20/04/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 15
25/05/2022	Executive Board	Remote	EB members	FCCIS Executive Board 16

3. FCC REVIEWS

3.1. REVIEW OF FCC PLACEMENT STUDIES

A review for the FCC placement studies took place at CERN in hybrid mode on 7 June 2021 (presentations and discussions) and on 8 June 2021 (closed session). The meeting was restricted to presenters, invited experts and reviewers.

Figure 2 – Review of FCC placement studies

Revue des études de placement FCC / Review of FCC placement studies (7-8 June 2021) · Indico (cern.ch)

3.1.1. Scope of the review

The FCC infrastructure is based on a 90 to 100 km circumference tunnel, connected via more or less regularly spaced access shafts with up to 12 surface sites. Placement of this infrastructure needs to take into account the underground geological conditions, territorial and environmental constraints as well as the physics performance that can be reached with the colliders. Final optimisation will also have to balance cost, risk and other aspects. Placement studies have commenced already during the conceptual design phase in cooperation with host state authorities. They were supported by civil engineering studies and the development of a geological model for the Geneva basin. Starting from the CDR baseline layout, various geometries and placements have been analysed. A down selection of these variants is the next logical step towards identification of a preferred placement variant that should then serve as reference for further studies on the feasibility of the entire FCC.

3.1.2. Review goals and charge

Review the status and methodology of FCC placement studies with the goal to support the down-selection of variants towards a preferred implementation scenario. Comment and advise on the following points and questions:

- **the methodology applied for the placement studies** (Given the multi-variate constraints, is the applied methodology fully adequate?)
- **the adequacy and relative importance of the boundary conditions and constraints identified** (Are the boundary conditions and constraints considered a full and adequate set? Have their relative importance been appropriately taken into account?)
- **the impact on physics/machine performance** (Is the impact on, and variation in, the machine performance of the various scenarios properly evaluated? For the favoured options, is it acceptable?)
- **the overall suitability of placement scenarios as basis for development of a preferred scenario** (Are the proposed placement scenarios a suitable basis for the development of a preferred scenario?)
- **the further planning and next steps of the placement optimisation process** (Are the proposed planning and next steps in the placement optimization process adequate and fit for purpose?)

3.1.3. Reviewers

Ralph Assmann (DESY), Günther Dissertori (ETHZ), Jean-François Hotellier (GADZ), Philippe Lebrun (JUAS), Yung Loo (ARUP), Steve Myers (ADAM SA), Franz Pacher (AMBERG), Andrew Parker (Cambridge U.), Nedim Radoncic (AMBERG), Bernhard Stacherl (GEOCONSULT), Matt Sykes (ARUP), Tim Watson (ITER)

3.1.4. Agenda

Table 3 – Review of FCC placement studies agenda

Presentation title	Presenter(s)
Methodology, conditions and constraints	Johannes Gutleber, Volker Mertens (CERN)
Civil engineering aspects and constraints	John Osborne (CERN)
Geological data gathering and 3 D geology model	Andrea Moscariello (UNIGE)
Overview on placement investigations	Johannes Gutleber (CERN), Volker Mertens (CERN)
Placement scenarios with 12 and 8 surface sites	Johannes Gutleber (CERN), Volker Mertens (CERN)
Assessment of scenarios from tunnelling/geological viewpoint	Stefan Eder (ILF Consulting Engineers), THOMAS Cyril (GADZ)

	SA), Werner Dallapiazza (ILF Zurich)
Optics and luminosity performance	Katsunobu Oide (KEK)
Beam transfer and injection scenarios	Wolfgang Bartmann (CERN)

3.1.5. Conclusions

A major layout and placement review was held on 7 and 8 June 2021, bringing together members of the FCC International Advisory Board, representatives of the host states and technical experts to review progress and confirm the methods applied. The development of a preferred scenario to be validated with subsurface investigations and with regional stakeholders is the next logical step. Link to presentation: https://indico.cern.ch/event/995850/contributions/4411829/attachments/2272033/3860047/FCC-2106140900-PBO_Territorial_Placement_V0004.pdf

3.2. PRE-ENGINEERING DESIGN REVIEW AND ROADMAP DISCUSSION FOR FCC-EE IR MAGNETS

A Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets took place at CERN in hybrid mode on 4 April 2022 (presentations and discussions) and on 5 April 2022 (closed session). The meeting was restricted to presenters, invited experts and reviewers.

The screenshot shows a meeting page with the following details:

- Title:** Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets
- Date/Time:** 4 Apr 2022, 14:00 → 5 Apr 2022, 19:00 Europe/Zurich
- Organizers:** Frank Zimmermann (CERN), Tor Raubenheimer (SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory (US))
- Description:** The FCC-ee IR magnet system must provide for low vertical beta function down to 0.8 mm, compensate for the coupling effect of the detector solenoid, and not introduce an unacceptable vertical emittance growth due to synchrotron radiation in magnet fringe fields. The baseline design consists of a pair of SC final quadrupoles (incoming and outgoing beams), inside a shielding solenoid, and an additional compensation solenoid between quadrupole and the interaction point. A magnet cryostat with internal skeleton is proposed to maximise the angular acceptance of the particle physics detector. Relative vibrations of the two beams in the frequency range above a few Hz should be limited to no more than a few nm. The IR magnet system should not quench for the expected level of beam loss or collision debris impacting in this region and be robust against realistic failure modes.
- Review goals and charge:** The review should evaluate the requirements on the IR quadrupoles and compensating solenoids, including the overall dimensions, angular stay-clear, magnetic fields including correction coils with frequency response, quadrupole/solenoid technology, operation temperature, apertures, alignment and stability, heat loads, and availability. Concepts and initial engineering considerations would also be discussed for implementation of the magnets and cryostat including concepts for the windings, correction coils, beam pipe, supports, cryostat and feedthroughs, alignment, stabilization, cooling, and access and maintenance.

Figure 3 – Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets
Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets (4-5 April 2022) · Indico (cern.ch)

3.2.1. Scope of the review

The FCC-ee IR magnet system must provide for low vertical beta function down to 0.8 mm, compensate for the coupling effect of the detector solenoid, and not introduce an unacceptable vertical emittance growth due to synchrotron radiation in magnet fringe fields. The baseline design consists of a pair of SC final quadrupoles (incoming and outgoing beams), inside a shielding solenoid, and an additional compensation solenoid between quadrupole and the interaction point. A magnet cryostat with internal skeleton is proposed to maximise the angular acceptance of the particle physics detector. Relative vibrations of the two beams in the frequency range above a few Hz should be limited to no more than a few nm. The IR magnet system should not quench for the

expected level of beam loss or collision debris impacting in this region and be robust against realistic failure modes.

3.2.2. Review goals and charge

Evaluate the requirements on the IR quadrupoles and compensating solenoids, including the overall dimensions, angular stay-clear, magnetic fields including correction coils with frequency response, quadrupole/solenoid technology, operation temperature, apertures, alignment and stability, heat loads, and availability. Discuss on the concepts and initial engineering considerations, for implementation of the magnets and cryostat including concepts for the windings, correction coils, beampipe, supports, cryostat and feedthroughs, alignment, stabilization, cooling, and access and maintenance.

3.2.3. Reviewers

Bernhard Auchmann (PSI / CERN), Stefania Farinon (INFN-GE), Patrick Janot (CERN), GianLuca Sabbi (LBNL), John Seeman, Chair (SLAC), Massimo Sorbi (INFN-Milano), Holger Witte (BNL), Akira Yamamoto (KEK).

3.2.4. Agenda

Table 4 - Pre-engineering design review and roadmap discussion for FCC-ee IR magnets agenda

Presentation title	Presenters
Introduction, high-level requirements and detector needs	Manuela Boscolo (INFN e Laboratori Nazionali di Frascati (IT)), Michael Kenneth Sullivan (SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory (US))
Requirements from Optics, fields, l*, and vibration tolerances	Katsunobu Oide (KEK)
CCT final quadrupole design, prototype and proposed cryostat, quench performance	Mike Koratzinos (MIT)
Experience with IR magnets from SuperKEKB	Norihito Ohuchi (KEK)
EIC IR magnet design	Holger Witte (Brookhaven National Laboratory)
IR alignment requirements and strategy	Leonard Watrelot (CNAM - Conservatoire National des Arts et Métiers (FR))

3.2.5. Conclusions

Excellent work has been done so far to define the concept of the FCC-ee IR • Repeated conversations with engineers had urged that we clarify a number of issues before trying to move further • The review helped to clarify what we have and what is missing • Detailed report in preparation with many recommendations • A lot of important input and feedback, also reference material from SuperKEKB and EIC

Many relevant suggestions to proceed with the pre-engineering IR magnets

https://indico.cern.ch/event/1140565/contributions/4825613/attachments/2424702/4150948/220411_IR_Review_boscolo.pdf

4. FCC ANNUAL MEETINGS

The annual conferences ‘FCC Week 2021’ and ‘FCC week 2022’ took place respectively in June 2021 and May 2022

- 28 June – 02 July 2021: Annual meeting FCC Week 2021 (remote) <https://indico.cern.ch/e/fccw2021>
- 30 May – 03 June 2022: Annual meeting FCC Week 2022 (hybrid mode, Paris, France) <https://indico.cern.ch/e/fccw2022>

Figure 4 – FCC Week 2022 poster

In addition, a new edition of the FCC Physics Workshop has been organized by the University of Liverpool in February 2022.

07 – 11 February 2022: FCC Physics Workshop (originally on site in Liverpool) [FCC Physics Workshop \(7-11 February 2022\): Overview · Indico \(cern.ch\)](#)

Figure 5 – 5th FCC Physics Workshop

5. CONTRIBUTIONS FOR OPEN ACCESS PROCEEDINGS PUBLICATION

Together with Springer/Nature, a beneficiary of the FCCIS consortium, the publication of a special issue of EPJ Plus (<https://www.springer.com/journal/13360>) focusing on FCC-ee was completed during 2021, based on the contributions given during the FCC November Week 2020.

The exact title of the special issue is “A future Higgs & Electroweak factory (FCC): Challenges towards discovery” and it include 34 essays covering the accelerator, experimental, theoretical and software challenges of the FCC-ee project. An international committee of 8 Guest Editors, together with the journal’s Editorial Board, has supervised the review process and ensured a high quality of the published essays.

The publication serves as a precious reference document, helping to evaluate the progress toward the realisation of FCCs since the publication of the FCC Conceptual Design Report, and covering in a concise, albeit solid way the challenges lying ahead for the accelerator design, experiments and detector development, the theoretical questions and, last but not least, the computational and software challenges that need to be tackled. Presenting the challenges and opportunities that a project like FCC offers can also inform a wider community of scientists and engineers working on similar topics and attract new partners from academia, research centres and the industry to the diverse and dynamic environment of the FCC study.

A second publication with Springer Nature is in preparation, for beginning of 2023. This publication is foreseen as an issue of EPJ Techniques & Instrumentation and will cover the R&D on FCC-ee, including aspects of machine-detector interface. The publication will be based mainly on presentation that were given at FCC Week 2022 in Paris.